

What Is Lost When Ghosts Are Found? The Problem of Certainty in Digital Game Adaptations

Ghosts have a peculiar charm: They are the ultimate unresolved entity. Whether rattling chains in Victorian novels or flickering as phantoms in Irish folk tales, ghosts thrive in ambiguity. Yet, when the spectral drifts into the digital, it seems the rules of the medium demand clarity, and therein lies a challenge.

Digital games like *Maid of Sker* (Wales Interactive, 2020) or Clive Barker's *Undying* (2001) transform what may have been the stuff of unsettled nightmares into manageable puzzles and neatly tied narrative threads. In doing so, they might just exorcise the very thing that makes ghosts fascinating: their defiance of closure.

This talk argues that games' insistence on "solving" hauntings undermines the ghost story's historical role. But can a medium like games resist the urge for resolution at all? Player agency, ultimately, thrives on control, but does this undermine the haunting's potency? Drawing from cultural studies theories like the Uncanny and hauntology and through examples like *The Excavation of Hob's Barrow* (Cloak and Dagger Games, 2002) and *The Lost Crown* (Darkling Room, Shadow Tor Studios, 2008), I will try to resolve—pun intended—the uneasy relationship between ghost stories and interactive storytelling.

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